

RESIDENTIAL PERSPECTIVES ON SOLAR POWER TECHNOLOGIES IN TANAUAN CITY, BATANGAS: LEVELS OF AGREEMENT AND OVERCOMING ADOPTION BARRIERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13120674>

ABSTRACT

The research delved into the dynamics of solar power technology adoption in Tanauan City, Batangas, a context marked by frequent power interruptions and steep electricity charges. Utilizing quota sampling and descriptive analysis, the study examined residents' attitudes, particularly focusing on awareness, affordability, infrastructure compatibility, and government policies. Results revealed a generally positive outlook, with 62% of respondents showing agreement across the dimensions of awareness and knowledge, affordability, infrastructure compatibility, and government incentives and policies. However, a substantial proportion of respondents remained neutral (28%) or held negative views (10%), indicating significant knowledge gaps and awareness deficiencies within the community. Identified challenges encompassed a lack of understanding about solar energy benefits, financial constraints hindering affordability perceptions, concerns about infrastructure readiness, and limited awareness regarding government initiatives supporting solar adoption. Action plans guided by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) suggested a focus on Photovoltaic (PV) solar technology. To address these issues, a multifaceted action plan was proposed: educational campaigns to bridge gaps, advocacy for financial support, infrastructure enhancement initiatives, and awareness campaigns on government policies. These efforts aimed to empower residents with knowledge and resources, fostering a sustainable future in Tanauan City, Batangas, and contributing to broader renewable energy transitions.

Keywords: *Residential Perspective, Solar Power Technologies, Awareness and Knowledge, Affordability, Infrastructure Compatibility, Government Policy, and Incentives,*

INTRODUCTION

Electricity is vital for daily life, which was crucial for industry, infrastructure, and societal well-being (Strielowski et al., 2021; IEEE Power and Energy Magazine, 2018). The impact of power outages on households and manufacturing firms emphasized the importance of electricity reliability and infrastructure development for safety, security, and economic development (Nduhuura 2021). The Philippines largely relied on fossil fuels to generate electricity, and challenges arose from disruptions in fossil fuel supplies due to Russia's invasion of Ukraine and the depletion of the Malampaya natural gas fields, which were projected to be exhausted by 2024 (ITA, 2022; Reuters, 2022).

In Batangas, Philippines, power outages raised significant concerns, especially for the safety and well-being of the community. The Batangas II Electric Cooperative, Inc. (BATELEC II), which supplied most of the power in the province, including Tanauan City, had a poor track record in promptly maintaining utility infrastructure and addressing line malfunctions, posing reliability challenges for electricity services. Furthermore, the challenges were intensified by much higher electricity costs, averaging 1.27 PHP per kWh, compared to other power providers (Source: BATELEC II & Meralco official websites), which added a burden to the vulnerable residents of Tanauan City.

Despite regional power challenges, Tanauan City underwent a transformative shift towards sustainable energy. According to the UN development program, Solar panels played a crucial role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by providing clean, renewable, and affordable energy solutions. These technologies were integral to addressing global challenges outlined in SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure). The study proposed a pioneering solution — the adoption of solar power technologies aimed at empowering communities to become independent energy generators, enhancing energy security, and contributing to sustainable economic development. The research examined several key dimensions that significantly influenced consumer perceptions and behaviors, including awareness and knowledge, affordability, infrastructure compatibility, and government policies and incentives.

Research Questions

The research questions guided the study by addressing specific concerns and achieving its objectives.

1. What factor/s influence/s the level of agreement among residents in Tanauan City, Batangas towards the possibility of using solar power technologies, in terms of the following dimensions:

- a. Awareness and Knowledge
- b. Affordability
- c. Infrastructure Compatibility
- d. Government Policies and Incentives

2. What are the barriers and challenges faced by residents in Tanauan City, Batangas when considering the adoption of solar power technologies as an alternative energy source along the following dimensions:

- a. Awareness and Knowledge
- b. Affordability
- c. Infrastructure Compatibility
- d. Government Policies and Incentives

3. What alternative solar power technologies can be adopted to address and minimize power disruptions in the communities?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design was a descriptive quantitative approach that systematically addressed the residents' perceptions of the four dimensions of factors, barriers, and alternative technologies related to solar power technology. The emphasis was on the structured examination, quantification, and measurement of acceptance levels, barriers, and the exploration of technological alternatives. The use of surveys and structured questionnaires enhanced objectivity and precision by collecting numerical responses. The systematic analysis of numerical data through statistical techniques contributed to the reliability, validity, and credibility of the research findings.

Research Locale

The research focused on selected communities in Tanauan City, Batangas, which had a population of 193,936 according to the 2020 Census. It was chosen because it experiences frequent power interruptions compared to other cities in Batangas. Additionally, its proximity to the researcher's location and time constraints for data collection influenced the selection. Conducting research in a familiar local context streamlined data collection and interaction with participants. The research aimed to provide alternative power solutions for Tanauan, addressing global energy resilience and environmental sustainability issues. Its goal was to improve the quality of life in Tanauan and effect real, positive change.

Sampling Method

The sampling method was quota sampling, with 100 respondents who were heads of households, decision-makers, or homeowners within families residing in Tanauan City,

Batangas. It was chosen to ensure diverse representation and allow the research to gather insights from those directly affected by energy challenges. Barangays were categorized into large, medium, and small size groups based on population density to capture diversity within the city, ensuring a representative sample.

In terms of Sex, 70% of respondents were male, and 30% were female, suggesting potential gender-specific factors influencing attitudes toward solar power adoption. The majority of respondents, 43%, fell within the age range of 31-40. In the category of Occupation, 68% were employed. Regarding the Household Level of Income, the majority (57%) fell below the 20K income bracket. Lastly, for Household Size, 43% of respondents had 3-4 members, while 35% had 5-6 members.

Research Instrumentation

A survey questionnaire was administered to the study's participants using an online survey tool or a conventional survey tool. In section I, questions focused on the profiling of the respondents, including gender, age, occupation, monthly income, and household size. In section II, there were three questions per dimension.

For Awareness and Knowledge (a), the questions aimed to assess respondents' understanding of solar power technology and its environmental benefits. Moving to Affordability (b), the questions delved into the financial aspect of solar adoption, probing residents' willingness to allocate a budget for solar technology installation, prioritize renewable energy sources, and their interest in government subsidies or incentives for solar adoption. Infrastructure Compatibility (c) questions focused on the practical considerations of integrating solar power systems into residences, including the suitability of roofs, readiness of electrical systems, and perceived convenience of integration. Lastly, Government Policies and Incentives (d) were evaluated through questions exploring residents' awareness of government support for solar adoption, utilization of incentives, and perceptions of government support.

Cronbach's alpha was calculated before the survey to evaluate the reliability of the 5-point Likert scale, which included demographics and four indicators: Awareness and Knowledge, Affordability, Infrastructure Compatibility, and Government Policies and Incentives. A pre-test at various locations in Batangas gathered responses from residents, which were used to assess the questionnaire's reliability before the survey began. A result of 0.70 or higher indicates that the instrument is reliable according to Statistical Consulting Group (2021). The Cronbach's alpha figures calculated are above the threshold with the equivalent of the summary result by 0.887 suggesting that all items in the established survey questionnaire were consistent. Thus, the questionnaire is reliable.

To verify that the questions contributed to the overall research objectives, they underwent content validity. Validators were asked to check each question and compare it with the research objectives to ensure that each question addressed an objective. During this process, the logical order of questions was also checked. Face validity was

also conducted, with a grammarian serving as one of the validators. Grammar, syntax, and mechanics were checked as part of language checking to ensure ease of answering on the part of the respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data was gathered either electronically or personally. After collecting the survey responses, they were tabulated to prepare for the next step in the research process: data analysis. This involved organizing the raw survey data into a structured format, typically using spreadsheet software or statistical analysis tools. Respondents ranked four dimensions in question 18, with one indicating the highest barrier to solar power adoption and four indicating the lowest. Question 19 in the survey was an open-ended question, valuable for investigating complex topics like solar power adoption in the area under review. These questions allowed for detailed and nuanced responses, offering insights beyond closed-ended questions.

Research Process Analysis

In the research study, descriptive analysis summarized key data insights by examining statistical measures like the percentage of agreement across demographic variables and the four dimensions. This approach identified patterns and trends, including residents' preferences for solar power benefits, and enabled subgroup comparisons by demographics, exploring variations in perceptions, barriers, and acceptance across population segments. Likert scale questions related to solar power adoption in the identified areas of dimensions were analyzed using frequency distribution to visualize response distribution, aiding in understanding agreement levels among respondents. Modal responses, representing common viewpoints, were particularly insightful.

Scope and Limitation

The study employed the quantitative research method to assess the level of agreement among Tanauan City residents on dimensions influencing their adoption of solar power technologies, including knowledge and awareness, affordability, infrastructure compatibility, and government policies and incentives. Using quota sampling, the study targeted 100 respondents who were heads of households, decision-makers, or homeowners within families residing in the area. While this approach aimed to capture diverse perspectives, it may not have entirely eliminated biases or ensured complete representativeness of the population.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RQ#1: Factor/s that Influence/s the Level of Agreement among residents in Tanauan City, Batangas

1.1 Awareness & Knowledge: The result indicated a significant portion expressing a combination of agreement and strong agreement related to solar literacy (68%), educational participation enhancing residential knowledge about the technology (82%), and the benefits of solar technology to the environment (70%). Studies by Kumar and Manish (2021) and Jiang et al. (2022) highlighted the role of understanding environmental benefits and education in influencing public perception and acceptance of solar power. Analyzing these findings through the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), residents' high agreement levels indicated perceived usefulness and ease of use of solar technology.

Overall, the Tanauan residents' attitudes toward solar power adoption revealed a majority awareness level of 62.3%, with 29.0% expressing neutrality and 8.7% disagreeing, highlighting the need for better education.

1.2 Affordability: The results highlighted the significant willingness of respondents to embrace solar power technology. 57% of respondents expressed readiness to allocate a portion of their budget for solar power installation, with an equal percentage prioritizing renewable energy source in household expenses. Moreover, 73% of respondents showed interest in availing government subsidies or incentives for solar power adoption. These findings resonate with existing literature emphasizing the financial attractiveness of solar power adoption and the role of government policies in promoting renewable energy. The results suggest a positive attitude toward the affordability of solar power technology among Tanauan residents, indicated a potential willingness to invest in renewable energy solutions with the right support mechanisms in place. Through the lens of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), respondents' attitudes aligned with the model's concepts of perceived usefulness and ease of use, reflecting their recognition of the benefits and feasibility of solar energy adoption, especially with external support.

Overall, the residential survey in Tanauan City, Batangas, highlighted affordability as a crucial factor in solar power adoption. While 62.3% of residents perceived solar technologies as affordable, 29.0% remained neutral, and 8.7% disagreed, indicating the need to address financial barriers and clarify long-term cost-effectiveness.

1.3 Infrastructure compatibility: The results illustrated varying levels of agreement among respondents regarding the compatibility of their infrastructure with solar power technology. A substantial percentage of respondents, totalling 61%, indicated that their roofs were suitable for solar panel installation, while 56% expressed positive perceptions about the readiness of their home's electrical system for solar panel integration, and an equal percentage found the integration of solar power technology convenient in their homes. However, a minority, ranging from 7% to 15%, disagreed or strongly disagreed with these statements. Addressing specific concerns raised by those expressing

disagreement or neutrality was crucial to facilitate widespread adoption, underscoring the need to overcome infrastructure-related challenges effectively.

Overall, the survey in Tanauan, Batangas revealed that 63.7% of residents perceived solar technologies as compatible with existing infrastructure, but 25% expressed doubts, indicating a need to address technical feasibility and reliability concerns. Smaller households showed higher confidence in roof suitability for solar panels, while larger households had more varied opinions, highlighting the need for tailored approaches.

1.4 Government Policies and Incentives: The results provided insights into varying levels of awareness and perception regarding government policies and incentives related to solar power adoption. For awareness, 46% of respondents indicated positive agreement, while 36% remained neutral, suggesting uncertainty. Regarding support for solar power adoption, 54% expressed positive interest, with 35% remaining neutral. Similarly, 74% perceived government support positively, while 20% remained neutral. A notable 7.2% disagreed with these statements on average. Analyzing through the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), respondents' perceived usefulness of government measures indicated potential barriers in understanding, reflected in the sizable neutral responses. While positive perceptions suggested the perceived usefulness of government initiatives, challenges in ease of use were apparent, impacting adoption readiness.

Overall, the survey in Tanauan City, Batangas revealed that while 57.7% of respondents agreed on the importance of government policies and incentives for solar power adoption, 30.3% were neutral and 12.0% disagreed, highlighting the need for improved transparency and accessibility.

RQ#2: Barriers & Challenges adoption of Solar Power Technologies faced by residents in Tanauan City, Batangas when considering the adoption of solar power technologies as an alternative energy source

2.1 Awareness & Knowledge: The survey in Tanauan City identified knowledge gaps and a lack of awareness hindering solar power adoption, particularly among specific demographic groups like lower-income households. Tailored educational initiatives targeted vulnerable populations and emphasized the benefits of solar technology. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) provided insights into addressing these barriers by focusing on users' perceptions and emphasizing the benefits and ease of use of solar technology.

2.2 Affordability: The survey highlighted affordability perceptions and financial barriers influencing solar power adoption, alongside concerns about high initial costs and regulatory uncertainties. Financial assistance programs and policy adjustments could lessen these barriers, while tailored communication strategies and the application of TAM principles enhanced affordability perceptions and promoted adoption.

2.3 Infrastructure Compatibility: Perceived infrastructure compatibility significantly influenced residential adoption of solar power technology, with positive perceptions correlating with higher adoption willingness. Holistic approaches involving awareness-building, tailored policies, and targeted incentives were necessary to address infrastructure compatibility concerns. TAM principles guided efforts to alleviate scepticisms and provide clear information, ensuring all segments of the population were equipped to make informed adoption decisions.

2.4 Government Policies and Incentives: It played a critical role in shaping solar power adoption, but awareness gaps existed among residents. Targeted education and communication efforts were essential to increase awareness and clarity about available support. TAM principles informed strategies to bridge the gap between interest and action, ensuring that information reached those who needed it most and facilitated wider adoption.

RQ#3: Alternative solar power technologies can be adopted to address and minimize power disruptions in Tanauan City

Table 1 shows the proposed solutions and strategies in general aimed at overcoming the identified barriers.

Table 1. General Proposed Solutions and Strategy

Dimension	Identified	Proposal Solution	Strategy
Awareness and Knowledge	Presence of knowledge gaps and lack of awareness	Targeted educational initiatives catering to vulnerable populations, providing easily accessible information on solar technology and its benefits. Emphasizing tangible benefits of solar technology (cost savings, sustainability) and simplifying the understanding and installation process. Collaborative efforts between stakeholders to amplify outreach and foster sustainable energy use.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct a knowledge gap assessment. 2. Develop educational materials. 3. Organize community workshop and events. 4. Partner with local organizations. 5. Implement door-to-door campaigns. 6. Utilize technology platforms.
Affordability	Affordability perceptions and financial barriers	Financial assistance programs (government subsidies) to alleviate upfront costs. Policy adjustments to reduce regulatory barriers and provide clarity on government support mechanisms. Tailored education and communication strategies addressing demographic-specific attitudes and priorities, highlighting long-term cost-saving benefits and providing clear information on subsidies and assistance programs.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raise awareness of government subsidies. 2. Conduct financial literacy workshops. 3. Engage with financial institutions. 4. Ensure transparent pricing information. 5. Explore community solar programs. 6. Offer incentives for early adopters.
Infrastructure Compatibility	Perceived infrastructure compatibility	Awareness-building, tailored policies, and targeted incentives. Disseminating accurate information and raising awareness about the compatibility of solar technology with various types of infrastructure.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide root assessment and consultations. 2. Organize technical assistance. 3. Streamline regulatory processes. 4. Arrange community demonstration. 5. Partner with homebuilders. 6. Develop online resources and tools.
Government Policies and Incentives	Lack of awareness regarding government initiatives	Targeted education and communication efforts, increasing awareness of government policies and incentives. Clarifying the process for accessing support and addressing uncertainties or skepticism through clear communication strategies,	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch information campaigns. 2. Facilitate government-community dialogues. 3. Advocate for local government support. 4. Create online portals for information. 5. Organize community outreach events. 6. Establish feedback mechanism.

In referenced survey data, barriers, and challenges in the adoption of solar technology by Tanauan City residents were identified. Photovoltaic (PV) Solar Cells, as shown in *Table 2*, emerged as the most suitable solar power technology for residential adoption. PV Solar Cells provided a renewable energy source, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and minimizing environmental impact. Their widespread recognition and understanding among residents helped address awareness gaps and facilitated educational programs about their benefits. Technological advances and economies of scale significantly lowered installation costs, making PV systems more affordable. Various financing options and government incentives further improved their economic viability. Lastly, PV Solar Cells were identified as the best choice for residential use in Tanauan due to their ease of installation and adaptability.

Table 2. Proposed Photovoltaic Technology Package

PV Solar Panel Type	System Configuration	Price (Ave)/ Efficiency	Warranties	Lifespan/Maintenance
Polycrystalline	Grid-Tied	₱ 180,000 Package / 15% ~ 17%	Panels - 25 ~ 30 years Inverters - 5 ~ 10 years	25 years / 2 ~3 years with cost of ₱2,500

Conclusions

The research study in Tanauan City revealed a multifaceted landscape of factors that influenced residents' attitudes toward solar power technologies. Insights emerged across dimensions such as Awareness and Knowledge, Affordability, Infrastructure Compatibility, and Government Policies and Incentives, shedding light on both barriers and potential solutions. Applying the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) focus on perceived usefulness and ease of use offered a structured framework for understanding perceptions, informing effective social action, policy development, and practical interventions. Awareness and Knowledge gaps were addressed through knowledge gap assessments and tailored educational materials. Affordability concerns were tackled by raising awareness of subsidies and financial literacy workshops. Infrastructure Compatibility issues were tackled through roof assessments and streamlined regulatory processes. Government Policies and Incentives awareness gaps were addressed through information campaigns and government-community dialogues. Stakeholders played a crucial role in fostering a favorable environment for solar adoption. Among solar technologies, PV Solar Cells emerged as the preferred option, with polycrystalline panels and grid-tied systems identified as suitable for residential adoption. Hybrid systems were proposed for blackout-prone areas. Achieving optimum adoption required balancing market demand, affordability, and regulatory support. Beyond addressing immediate energy needs, the adoption of solar power aligned with broader Sustainable Development Goals. Solar technology not only supported SDG 7 by promoting access to affordable and clean energy but also contributed significantly to SDG 13 by mitigating climate change impacts and advanced SDG 9 through innovation in renewable energy infrastructure.

Overall, the study laid the groundwork for advancing solar technology adoption in Tanauan City, Batangas, Philippines.

Recommendations

Research Question #1: Future studies delved deeper into demographic factors that influenced perceptions of solar affordability, such as differences across age groups, educational backgrounds, socio-economic status, and family income. Additionally, Future research should explore the effectiveness of community-based educational programs and outreach activities in improving residents' understanding of solar energy benefits. Involving communities in knowledge-sharing initiatives identified culturally relevant communication strategies and tailored educational materials to local needs.

Research Question #2: Barriers to solar power adoption, such as misconceptions and lack of trust, can be addressed through community engagement initiatives. Future studies aimed to investigate the impact of community-led initiatives on overcoming adoption barriers, with a focus on social norms and perceived risks. Further study was needed to enhance solar power cost analysis for informed decision-making, considering initial investment costs, long-term cost-effectiveness, and government incentives. Challenges included data complexities, requiring collaboration and monitoring of attitudes and adoption rates to gauge effectiveness.

Research Question #3: Tailoring alternative solar power technologies to local needs and conditions could enhance community resilience. Future research aimed to explore community preferences and priorities regarding solar technology options, ensuring solutions met specific needs and preferences. Additionally, conducting an in-depth analysis of neutral results was recommended to determine their influence on adoption rates and develop targeted interventions. Delving into the reasons behind neutral sentiments provided valuable insights for refining strategies aimed at promoting the widespread adoption of solar energy. Furthermore, in addressing barriers, several key factors were considered when planning solar installations, such as location and roof orientation, energy needs, cost and incentives, contracting company, durability, project length, and return on investment. Additionally, the research could explore the effectiveness of various types of solar power systems (e.g., off-grid, on-grid, hybrid) in meeting diverse consumer needs and preferences.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research study on solar power adoption in Tanauan City, Batangas, emphasized rigorous ethical considerations integral to its design and execution. Under the guidance and approval of the Letran Graduate School, the study employed closed-ended questions with predetermined response options to gather data. Ethical principles were woven throughout, beginning with the paramount issue of informed consent. Participants were meticulously informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits, ensuring their participation was voluntary and fully understood.

Confidentiality was another cornerstone of the study's ethical framework. Participants' privacy was rigorously protected through anonymization of data and secure storage practices, safeguarding their responses from identification or misuse. The ethical guidelines also prioritized respecting local customs and ensuring transparency in communication. This commitment to transparency extended to openly sharing research objectives, methodologies, and findings with the community, fostering trust and collaboration.

Acknowledgments

I humbly dedicate this thesis to our Lord Jesus Christ, whose unwavering support provided me with the strength, wisdom, and fortitude to navigate through the challenges encountered in this study. I am profoundly grateful to the Almighty for granting me this achievement. To You, O God, be all the glory!

I extend my heartfelt appreciation to my partner Maricar M. Marzan, my family; mother, siblings, and especially my son, Marcus Erastus Klaus M. Castillo, for their unwavering assistance, support, and encouragement during the trials faced along this arduous journey. Their presence has been my constant inspiration, and I cherish all of them.

I express my sincere thanks to Collins Aerospace-B. V Philippine Branch for granting me the opportunity to be a recipient of their scholarship, enabling me to complete my studies.

To my esteemed thesis adviser & Co-Author, Dr. Evangeline T. Pasion, I am deeply indebted for your invaluable guidance, unwavering support, and constructive feedback, which significantly contributed to the refinement of my thesis. I am also grateful to Dr. Maria Milagrosa M. Ocenar and Dr. Lalaine B. Ocampo, our research coordinators, for their insightful guidance and invaluable inputs that significantly contributed to the success of my study.

My sincere appreciation extends to my esteemed panelists, Dr. Mariano M. Delos Santos, Dr. Marie Joy Q. Elomina, and Engr. Christopher V. Gonzales, for generously sharing their expertise and providing valuable insights that enhanced the quality of my research.

Special thanks to my statistician, Dr. John Jesus D. Meneses, for his expert guidance and insightful analysis, which greatly aided in the clear interpretation of the gathered data.

To all who have contributed to this endeavor, whether directly or indirectly, your support has been instrumental in the fulfillment of this academic pursuit. Thank you all for your unwavering encouragement and support.

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